

EFFECT OF PREOPERATIVE ANXIETY ON PREOPERATIVE HEMODYNAMICS AND POST OPERATIVE RECOVERY AND PAIN IN ENDOSCOPY ULTRASONOGRAPH

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Abstract

Background:

Increased heart rate, blood pressure, and SpO₂ levels were observed to significantly associated with greater anxiety ratings in patients having elective cholecystectomy. Finding shows that heart rate and blood pressure were significantly associated with preoperative anxiety during EUS. Anxiety has an impact on these physiological responses as seen by raised heart rates and blood pressure seen in patients with severe anxiety. Preoperative anxiety includes worrying about the procedure, worrying about the outcome, being away from the family, anticipating postoperative pain, losing one's freedom, and fearing both surgery and death.

Methods:

In this cross-sectional study, the focus is on investigating the connection between preoperative anxiety and its impact on the perception of pain and physiological parameters in patients having Endoscopic Ultrasonography (EUS) at Shaikh Zayed Hospital in Lahore, Punjab. 60 patients (36 female and 24 male) having EUS were chosen using a selective sample strategy. Their ages ranged from 20 to 70. The GAD-7 scale was used to assess the degree of anxiety, and the Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) was used to assess the severity of pain. Hemodynamic information, such as breathing rate, oxygen saturation, blood pressure, and heart rate, was obtained before the procedure. We entered and analyzed the data using IBM-SPSS version 23.0 for statistical analysis.

Results:

The degree of heart rate (p -value = 0.024), blood pressure (p -value = 0.039) also pain (p -value = 0.026) so all of these are significantly correlated with preoperative anxiety. During the operation, those with higher anxiety levels felt more intense pain and raised heart rates. However, there were no statistically significant relationships found between preoperative anxiety and oxygen saturation (p -value = 0.055) or respiratory rate (p -value = 0.093). Patients having EUS experience substantial effects from preoperative anxiety on their sense of pain and heart rate. Patients who had more anxiety throughout the operation reported feeling more pain and had faster heart rates. These results underline how crucial it is to deal with preoperative anxiety in order to maximise patient comfort and procedural success.

Conclusion:

There is significant association between preoperative anxiety and pain, heart rate, and blood pressure in the patient under going EUS. Preoperative anxiety and

respiratory rate or oxygen saturation, however, did not appear to be significantly associated. This implies that anxiety might not have a major impact on these particular physiological markers during the EUS technique.

INTRODUCTION

An unpleasant feeling that involves fear, tension, and discomfort is referred to as anxiety (1). Surgery can be traumatic, causing bleeding, pain, and even death. Anxiety is common among patients and should be addressed with preoperative measures. Waiting for surgery is stressful and affects patients both physically and mentally (2). Preoperative anxiety impacts surgical outcomes, raising the risk of bleeding, hypertension, and increased postoperative pain

medication needs (3). Anxiety is a stress response to specific situations, influenced by both external triggers and an individual's predisposition to stress (4). Individual variations in personality traits and preoperative anxiety influence patient outcomes. Different personalities have diverse coping abilities for stress, which impacts postoperative outcomes. These complexities highlight the importance of understanding these factors in patient care (5).

Figure No.1.1: Personality, anxiety, and postoperative outcomes.

It is an unpleasant state of tension, triggering abnormal physiological responses. It starts when surgery is planned and peaks upon hospital admission (6). Preoperative anxiety is a common response to the uncertain and potentially intimidating nature of surgery, particularly for first-time patients. Research indicates that high levels of preoperative anxiety can result in greater postoperative pain medication needs, longer hospital stays, and negative preoperative outcomes, leading to low patient satisfaction (7).

The circulatory system includes the heart and blood vessels, responsible for transporting oxygen, nutrients, heat, and other substances throughout the body. In medical contexts, "hemodynamics" refers to the study of blood flow and the related physical properties of the cardiovascular system, such as arterial pressure and cardiac output (8). This definition primarily focuses on the mechanics of fluids and solids in the system, while acknowledging the significant role of biological processes that interact with

hemodynamic effects without detailed discussion (9). Preoperative anxiety and hemodynamic changes during laryngoscopy and intubation can lead to surgery cancellation. Informing patients

preoperatively reduces anxiety, fear, depression, postoperative pain medication needs, and shortens hospital stays (10, 11).

Figure No.1.2 Hemodynamic

Preoperative anxiety is highly prevalent, affecting up to 80% of patients undergoing high-risk surgeries. It has been shown to have negative psychological and physical effects, impacting postoperative care, treatment, rehabilitation and anesthesia. It is also thought to be a risk factor for post-operative mortality (12). Due to the anticipated bodily reaction induced by having surgery, predicting postoperative recovery would have substantial clinical and theoretical relevance. Surgery itself causes a bodily reaction that is largely anticipated because it is a momentous event. During the preoperative phase, affective elements, especially anxiety, play a crucial role (13). Preoperative anxiety and pain sensitivity have an effect on a variety of factors, including the quantity of anaesthesia used, preoperative recovery time, postoperative pain, and hemodynamics. It can help to improve preoperative care to know how pain sensitivity, preoperative anxiety, and anaesthesia needs are related (14).

The Hamilton Anxiety Scale (HAM-A), which is frequently used to evaluate general anxiety

symptoms across a range of circumstances, is an essential instrument for diagnosing generalised anxiety disorder (GAD). This strategy is frequently used as the main technique for evaluating anxiety in treatment outcome studies (15). Measurements of generalised anxiety disorder are made using the GAD-7 scale (16). The GAD-7 scale utilizes a measurement system based on a series of seven questions. Each question asks individuals to rate their experiences related to anxiety symptoms is determined by ranging of scale from 0 to 3, where 0 is representing "not at all" and 3 is representing "nearly every day." This standardized tool aids in diagnosis and monitoring the progress of individuals with GAD. Symptom scores range from 0 to 21, representing different frequencies of occurrence. Total scores can vary from 0 to 21, with the thresholds for mild, moderate, and severe anxiety being 5, 10, and 15 respectively. When screening for an anxiety disorder, a score of 10 or above is advised for referral for additional assessment (17).

GAD-7				
Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems?	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
1. Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge	0	1	2	3
2. Not being able to stop or control worrying	0	1	2	3
3. Worrying too much about different things	0	1	2	3
4. Trouble relaxing	0	1	2	3
5. Being so restless that it is hard to sit still	0	1	2	3
6. Becoming easily annoyed or irritable	0	1	2	3
7. Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen	0	1	2	3
Total Score = — = — + — + —				

Figure No.1.3 GAD-7 Scale for anxiety

Before to the preparation of any necessary educational, medical, or psychological treatments, the degree of anxiety should be assessed. This evaluation should be viewed as an integral aspect of preoperative care. Anxiety levels can be assessed using psychometric measures (12). Many people may have a variety of fear and anxiety before to surgery or any other medical procedure such as (Endoscopic Ultrasonography). These include anxiety, fear of pain following surgery, fear of not waking up after anaesthetic, and fear of passing away. Preoperative anxiety has grown to be a serious mental health problem for many people undergoing surgery as a result of these worries (18).

To make it clearer, non-pharmacological interventions refer to a variety of methods that can be employed to treat a patient's condition. These methods might involve healthcare providers conducting interviews, communication strategies, visits from family members, acupuncture, different ways to divert attention, participation in religious or spiritual activities, listening to music, and providing patient education (Figure No.1) (19). Benzodiazepines can be given to address sudden or acute symptoms of anxiety, but chronic anxiety usually requires more comprehensive treatment. Medication, psychotherapy, or a combination of both can effectively manage chronic anxiety (20).

Figure No.1.4 Non-Pharmacological Methods For Managing Preoperative Anxiety

Endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS) is a diagnostic and treatment method that is commonly used today. When performing EUS on patients, it is now standard practice to administer intravenous sedation (21). It uses a specialized endoscope with a high-frequency ultrasound transducer at its tip. This transducer emits sound waves and creates precise images by receiving the echoes from tissues. EUS has two scanning methods: radial scanning for cross-sectional images and sector scanning for a wider field of view. It helps visualize organs like the esophagus, stomach, pancreas, and liver, aiding in lesion detection, biopsies, cancer staging, and treatment monitoring. EUS is essential in diagnosing and managing gastrointestinal conditions, improving patient care and outcomes (22). EUS is mostly used to view the gastrointestinal tract, with the help of modified endoscope and combines it with high frequency ultrasound. This allows for accurate imaging of the various layers of the

gastrointestinal wall and assessment of structures outside of the gastrointestinal tract. This combination of technologies allows for more precise imaging and better assessment of areas that may require therapeutic intervention (23). Endoscopic ultrasound (EUS) is valuable due to its capacity to visualize the layers of the gut wall, correlating with histological layers. Additionally, it can clearly show the pancreatic-biliary region, lymph nodes and masses that are near to the gut wall. These features make EUS useful for various diagnostic purposes (24, 25). The easiest way to track the level of anaesthesia is with the BIS (Bispectral Index). Currently, BIS monitoring is more useful for determining the level of sedation since it is less susceptible to outside influences. In actuality, during these kinds of surgeries, we typically administer further doses of propofol based on the symptoms, vital signs, and BIS of the patient (14).

Figure No.1.5 Endoscopy Ultrasonography

For people with high blood pressure and coronary artery disease, inadequate pain management can be life-threatening. If these patients undergo physiological stress due to pain, they are at risk of a stroke or myocardial infarction, respectively (26). When the sympathetic nervous system becomes highly activated, it triggers a cascade of physiological responses, including elevated metabolic rate, heart rate, heart contractility, and increased

oxygen consumption by heart. For individuals with narrowed coronary arteries, this heightened stress can lead to a heart attack. Moreover, postoperative pain puts additional strain on the heart, increasing the risk of mortality. In hypertensive patients, intensified pain can cause a significant rise in blood pressure, potentially resulting in a stroke due to cerebral hemorrhage. Furthermore, inadequate management of postoperative pain may contribute to the

development of chronic pain conditions, such as post thoracotomy pain. Proper pain control and cardiovascular monitoring are essential to mitigate these risks (27).

Pain is subjective, varying among individuals, and can only be understood by the sufferer. It triggers a neuroendocrine response, increasing tone in visceral organs and releasing catecholamines from the adrenal medulla. Hormonal reactions stem from heightened sympathetic tone and reflexes mediated by the hypothalamus (27, 28).

Typically healthcare providers request patients to use a Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) to indicate their level of pain by selecting a number between 0 and 10, 0 and 20, or 0 and 100. A rating of 0 on the scale usually indicates that the patient is not experiencing any pain, while the highest possible rating represents the most severe pain imaginable (29) In various studies, there have been strong correlations observed between Numerical Rating Scales and other tools used for assessing pain (30).

Figure No.1.6 Scale NRS (Numerical Rating Scales)

Chung and colleagues used subjective clinical evaluation in their investigation to gauge the level of anaesthesia. Their findings indicated that there was no association between anxiety levels and the amount of anesthesia consumed (31). However, there was a limitation in the methodology of the study, as the authors faced challenges in accurately determining the precise amount of anesthetics consumed using the subjective clinical observation method. Other clinical trials attempted to overcome this issue by utilizing a BIS (Bispectral Index) the monitor, but the outcomes obtained were not consistent across these trials (32, 33).

A 2022 study found that most surgical patients were male (64.4%) and aged between 20-46 years (48.3%). Preoperative anxiety was often modest in patients, whereas the preoperative anxiety that was significant was rather uncommon. Preoperative anxiety showed the higher prevalence among females, younger patients, and those undergoing valvular procedures ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, the timing of the surgery significantly predicted anxiety related to anesthesia and the procedure ($p < 0.05$) (34). Understanding the impact of preoperative anxiety on patients in Pakistan, where medical

procedures are common, is crucial. This study seeks to assess the relationship between preoperative anxiety and preoperative hemodynamics, postoperative recovery time, and pain experienced during endoscopic ultrasonography. The findings will shed light on effective interventions to enhance patient experiences.

Statement of Problem

According to the Pakistan Association of Cognitive Therapists (PACT), anxiety is fairly common in Pakistan, affecting over 25% of people at some time in their lives. A frequent issue that can cause issues both before and after medical procedures is anxiety before surgery. It is a common occurrence that has the potential to harm patient outcomes, particularly post-operative recovery time and pain as well as preoperative hemodynamics. The primary goal of this study is to examine the potential effects of preoperative anxiety on these variables in patients undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography. Preoperative anxiety can have a severe impact on a patient's physical and mental health, which can result in undesirable consequences including worsened pain, a slower rate of recovery, and a

longer hospital stay. Understanding the link between preoperative anxiety and patient outcomes is essential for enhancing patient care. Investigating this connection is crucial.

Objectives

Objectives of our study are:

- To investigate the incidence of preoperative anxiety among patients in Pakistan having endoscopic ultrasonography.
- To evaluate how preoperative anxiety effects on preoperative hemodynamics in patients undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography.
- To evaluate how preoperative anxiety affects the recovery and pain experienced by patients having endoscopic ultrasonography.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the study by Bayrak *et al.*, which involved 72 patients having elective cholecystectomy, researchers find out that age had no significant impact on anxiety levels. Increased heart rate, blood pressure, and SpO₂ levels were all linked to higher anxiety ratings. Throughout the first 24 hours following surgery, Group 1 had lower pain scores, higher SpO₂ readings, and less tramadol intake than Group 2. The two groups consumed tenoxicam differently at particular times (10).

In 2022, Sadaf *et al.*, conducted a cross-sectional study in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, aiming to examine preoperative anxiety levels in patients undergoing open-heart surgery at cardiac centers. Among the 180 participants selected for open-heart surgery, 64.4% were male, and 48.3% fell in the 20-46 age group. The study revealed a higher prevalence of preoperative anxiety in females, younger patients, and those undergoing valvular surgeries (p value < 0.05). Moreover, the timing of the surgery emerged as a significant predictor of anxiety associated with anesthesia and the procedure (p value < 0.05). These findings underscore the importance of comprehending preoperative anxiety's consequences in a region where medical procedures are prevalent, and offer valuable insights to improve patient care and experiences

during endoscopic ultrasonography (34).

Zhang *et al.*, investigated the correlation among preoperative anxiety and postoperative pain in female patients receiving laparoscopic hysterectomy in a study published in 2021. One hundred participants were split into two groups at random. The preoperative self-rating anxiety scale (SAS) score on average was 40.99 ± 4.55, which was higher than the Chinese average. While education levels did not, occupation and surgical experience significantly affected preoperative SAS scores. In comparison to group B, group A had higher postoperative numerical rating scale (NRS) ratings. A positive association between SAS and NRS scores was seen in both groups (35).

Ferda *et al.*, investigated eighty patients who underwent sedation-assisted endoscopic ultrasonography in a 2021 study. Before the procedure, patients completed the Pain Sensitivity Questionnaire (PSQ) and State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI). Sedation was achieved using midazolam, lidocaine, fentanyl, and propofol. The findings revealed a significant correlation between preoperative anxiety and patient's pain sensitivity across various variables. The visual analogue scale (VAS) at 1 hour after surgery showed stronger associations with STAI-T and STAI-S when compared to PSQ. However, at the 2-hour mark after surgery, only STAI-T and STAI-S exhibited substantial connections with pain sensitivity (21).

In the study by Daniel, *et al.*, four of the 5906 papers found during the literature search were chosen for examination. These were three reported in 2003, 2007 and 2020 randomised clinical studies carried out in European hospitals. In the analysis of pain management options, surgical therapy demonstrated higher rates of full pain control compared to endoscopic treatment, while the incidence of new endocrine or exocrine failure showed no significant differences. The study evaluated baseline characteristics and outcome measures, including pain management, the quality of life, and functional outcomes. A meta-analysis further supported the superiority of surgery in providing pain relief. However, no significant variations were observed in failure

rates or quality of life among the different treatment approaches. These findings highlight the potential benefits of surgical interventions for effective pain control in comparison to endoscopic methods, without compromising overall quality of life (36).

In a study conducted in 2021 by Maria *et al.*, they explored the connection between anxiety, gender differences, and heart health. With an average age of 66.8 years and a gender ratio of 45%, the research comprised 291 individuals who underwent cardiac stress testing. The study aimed to ascertain whether trait anxiety, assessed through a questionnaire, and state anxiety, gauged using facial expression recognition software, correlated with ischemia, a condition characterized by reduced blood supply to the heart. According to the study, for the whole participant group, there was no significant correlation between the prevalence of ischemia and either state or trait anxiety. However, breaking down the data by gender and age revealed an intriguing pattern. More likely to experience ischemic heart disease, older women tend to be anxious. No state anxiety was present during this exchange. The research results point out that trait anxiety can lead to disparities in heart functionality between men and women during cardiac stress tests. It is noteworthy to mention that the relationship found is between trait anxiety and not state anxiety (37).

In a study conducted in 2006 by Zeev *et al.*, in this study, the impact of preoperative anxiety on postoperative recovery was investigated in 241 kids between the ages of

5 and 12 who were undergoing tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy. The results showed that because worried youngsters experienced more pain during their hospital stay and the first three days at home, they required higher dosages of medications. Additionally, they had a higher prevalence of sleep problems, postoperative anxiety, and developing delirium than children who were not anxious. These findings indicate that preoperative anxiety in young children is linked to a more challenging postoperative recovery and an increased risk of sleep issues and other issues. It highlights how crucial it is to treat

young patients who are having surgery for preoperative anxiety (38).

In research published in 2020, Sergiu *et al.*, this study found that 18.5% of patients had severe anxiety and fear. In the operating room, researchers looked at patients' perceptions of pain and anxiety. According to the research, the relationship between the VAS and the VASA ($r = 0.62$, $p .001$) showed that individuals who felt anxious had more pain. Longer surgeries were associated with higher pain levels, according to a positive correlation between VAS ratings and surgical time ($r = 0.20$, $p = .04$). No further factors connected to VAS were discovered by univariate analysis. High VASA score individuals who suffer from a severe anxiety disorder may experience intense pain. The evidence shows that since anxiety influences post-operative experiences and pain perception, it might be helpful to assess and manage anxiety levels before surgery. Using certain measures, doctors can increase patient comfort and outcomes by acknowledging this relationship (39).

In a study conducted in 2010 by Won-Sung *et al.*, a significant association between state anxiety levels and during anaesthesia induction percentage changes in mean blood pressure and heart rate was seen in the subgroup of patients aged 45 or older. Significant associations between state anxiety levels and changes in vital signs were seen among several subgroups. Patients who were 45 years of age or older in particular demonstrated state anxiety levels as reliable indicators of a 20% change in vital signs during induction. However, no significant association between state anxiety levels and changes in vital signs was discovered in other subgroups. These results emphasise the need of measuring anxiety levels, particularly in the older patient group, as it might be a useful tool for anticipating physiological reactions during anaesthesia induction (11).

In a study conducted in 2020 by Jorge *et al.*, the initial study that involved 50 patients admitted for M3M extraction included 47 patients who met the criteria, who were divided into a video group (25 patients) and a control group (22 patients). The audience who watched the video

was less nervous according to the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory and the Modified Dental Anxiety Scale as shown by bivariate analysis. The video group also displayed a lower heart rate. While controlling for STAI-Trait, a linear regression analysis has upheld the reduced dental anxiety levels found by the MDAS in the video group. These outcomes reaffirm that videos are helpful in minimizing dental stress in individuals who are undergoing M3M extraction. The utilization of videos can significantly decrease patients' uneasiness and enhance the general experience during dental procedures (40).

In a study conducted in 2013 by Achmet *et al.*, a strong correlation was found between the preoperative Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) score and the length of hospitalisation, with preoperative anxiety affecting 31 (38.75%) of all patients. Patient recovery was quicker, there were fewer extubations, and it took less time for group L patients to obtain a modified Aldrete score of 9. Additionally, group L saw less negative surgery outcomes. Patients in group L also reported lower VAS scores for postoperative pain and used less tramadol for pain management. According to these findings, treating preoperative anxiety and employing certain therapies (group L) can result in better recovery outcomes, less postoperative pain, and a lesser need for painkillers. In addition, group L required less tenoxicam than the other groups did. These results emphasise the possible advantages of applying certain interventions or methods, as represented by group L, to enhance surgical results, such as quicker recovery, lower pain, and reduced pharmaceutical needs (41).

METHODOLOGY

Study design:

Descriptive cross sectional study design was used.

Study setting:

Data was collected from Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore, Punjab.

Sample Technique:

The purposive sampling technique was used.

Sample size:

A total of 60 samples of Endoscopic Ultrasonography patients were conducted from Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore, Punjab.

Sample selection criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- Data of patients aged 20-70 of both genders undergoing Endoscopic Ultrasonography were used.
- Patients who could comprehend and complete the anxiety evaluation measures were eligible to take part in the trial.
- Data from patients who had anxiety before surgery was used..

Exclusion criteria:

- Endoscopic Ultrasonography requiring an invasive procedure was excluded.
- Patients with cognitive impairment or language problems who were unable to complete the anxiety evaluation measures or comprehend the instructions were excluded.
- Patients who may have a different response to therapies for anxiety management due to a history of drug abuse or dependency were not included.

Procedure: Patients at Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore who were scheduled for endoscopies provided the data. Before the operation, they answered the GAD-7 questionnaire to rate their level of anxiety during the previous two weeks. There are four degrees of anxiety according to the GAD-7 scale. Patients were asked about possible anxiety triggers as well. Prior to endoscopy, hemodynamic data were collected to take into consideration physiological baseline values. Patients used the Pain Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), which ranges from 0 to 10, to quantify their level of pain following the surgery. The study provided important insights into effect of anxiety on patients' procedural experiences by examining the association between anxiety levels and pain felt during endoscopy.

Data collection tool:

A Performa was used to collect data from the patient undergoing Endoscopic Ultrasonography, and the Performa was developed with help of expert opinion.

Sysmex Numerical Rating Scale (NRS):

To determine how severe someone's pain is, utilise the straightforward and popular Numeric

Rating Scale (NRS) pain scale. It involves asking participants to rate their level of pain from 0 to 10, with 0 signifying "no pain" and 10 denoting "the worst pain imaginable pain." In order to help medical professionals determine the extent of the patient's suffering, patients simply choose a number that represents the amount of pain they are feeling.

Figure No.3.1 Scale NRS (Numerical Rating Scales)

Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7 (GAD-7):

The GAD-7 scale, commonly known as the Generalised Anxiety Disorder 7-item scale, is a well-liked self-report questionnaire created to evaluate the severity of symptoms of generalised anxiety disorder (GAD). The test consists of seven questions and measures the frequency and severity of anxiety symptoms during the past two weeks. On the GAD-7 scale, each response corresponds to a specific anxiety symptom, such

as feeling tight or on edge, finding it difficult to control concerns, and restlessness. Respondents rate their experiences on a scale of 0 to 3; higher ratings suggest more severe symptoms. Scores from answers to each question are added up to produce the range from 0 to 21. Higher scores represent more significant levels of anxiety, whereas lower values represent negligible or no anxiety.

GAD-7				
Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems?	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
1. Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge	0	1	2	3
2. Not being able to stop or control worrying	0	1	2	3
3. Worrying too much about different things	0	1	2	3
4. Trouble relaxing	0	1	2	3
5. Being so restless that it is hard to sit still	0	1	2	3
6. Becoming easily annoyed or irritable	0	1	2	3
7. Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen	0	1	2	3

Total Score = ___ = ___ + ___ + ___

Figure No.3.2 GAD-7 Scale for anxiety

Data analysis:

SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) used for data analysis. Fisher's exact test or the chi-squared test was used to analyze nominal data. On a personal laptop, data analysis was carried out using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 25.

male and 36 of whom were female, who had endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS) procedures. These patients were chosen because endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS) was their primary course of treatment. The study's gender distribution shows that women make up the majority of participants, accounting for about 60% (36 out of 60), while men make up about 40% (24 out of 60) of the study's participants.

RESULTS

The study included 60 patients, 60 of whom were

Table No. 4.1 Gender-based distribution of EUS

Gender Of Patient		
Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	36	60.0%
Male	24	40.0%
Total	60	100.0%

Figure No. 4.1 Gender-based distribution of EUS

Examining the association between preoperative anxiety and postoperative pain in patients undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS):

Table No.4.2 Association between preoperative anxiety and patient's pain level

Anxiety Level * Pain Level Crosstabulation					
		Pain Level			Total
		Mild Pain	Moderate Pain	Sever Pain	
Mild Anxiety		2	8	1	11

Anxiety Level	Moderate Anxiety	6	13	2	21
	Sever Anxiety	4	11	13	28
Total		12	32	16	60
P-value			0.026		

Table 4.2 shows a p-value of 0.26, which indicates there is a significant association between preoperative anxiety and patient's pain levels during endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS). According to table 4.2, there were 11 (18.33%) patients who had mild anxiety, 21 (35%) patients who experienced moderate anxiety, and 28 (46.66%) patients who experienced severe anxiety.

Examining the association between preoperative anxiety and Respiratory Rate of the patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS):

Table No.4.3 Association between preoperative anxiety and patient's respiratory rate

Anxiety Level * Respiraterey Rate Of The Patients Crosstabulation		Respiraterey Rate Of The Patients										Total
		12	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	22	24	
Anxiety Level	Mild Anxiety	1	0	1	2	3	2	0	0	1	1	11
	Moderate Anxiety	0	7	3	4	3	4	0	0	0	0	21
	Sever Anxiety	0	7	3	7	0	4	1	3	3	0	28
Total		1	14	7	13	6	10	1	3	4	1	60
P-vlaue			0.093									

Table 4.3 shows a p-value of 0.093, which indicates insignificant results. The findings suggest that there is no significant association between preoperative anxiety and their respiratory rate of patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS).

Examining the correlation between preoperative anxiety and Heart Rate of the patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS):

Table No.4.4 Association between preoperative anxiety and patient's heart rate

Anxiety Level * Heart Rate Of The Patients Crosstabulation		Heart Rate Of The Patients																			Total
		68	70	72	75	78	80	82	84	85	88	90	91	94	95	96	98	99	100	105	

Mild Anxiety	0	2	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Moderate Anxiety	2	0	2	2	1	3	0	0	0	3	4	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	21
Sever Anxiety	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	6	3	4	4	1	2	28
Total	2	3	3	3	4	4	1	1	1	6	6	1	1	1	7	3	4	5	1	3	60
P-vlaue	0.024																				

Table 4.4 shows a p-value of 0.024, which indicates significant results. The results shows there is a significant association between preoperative anxiety and heart rate of the patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS).

Examining the association between preoperative anxiety and Oxygen saturation of the patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS):

Table No.4.5 Association between preoperative anxiety and patient's saturation

		Oxygen Saturation Of The Patients												Total
		100%	80%	87%	90%	92%	93%	94%	95%	96%	97%	98%	99%	
Anxiety Level	Mild Anxiety	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	7	11
	Moderate Anxiety	3	1	0	1	1	1	0	4	0	3	5	2	21
	Sever Anxiety	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	3	5	6	2	8	28
Total		3	1	1	3	1	1	2	7	5	10	9	17	60
P-vlaue		0.055												

According to Table 4.5, the obtained p-value is 0.055, indicating that the results are insignificant. The results show that there is no association between preoperative anxiety and oxygen saturation of the patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS).

Examining the association between preoperative anxiety and Blood pressure of the patient undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS):

Table No.4.6 First 16 patient’s association between preoperative anxiety and blood pressure

Anxiety Level * Blood Pressure Of The Patients Crosstabulation											
Blood Pressure Of The Patients											
	100/80	110/70	110/75	110/80	110/90	115/70	120/70	120/75	120/80	122/85	Total
Mild Anxiety	0	1	0	2	2	1	1	0	2	0	9
Moderate Anxiety	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	7
Sever Anxiety	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	4	1	16

Table No.4.7 next 20 patient’s association between preoperative anxiety and blood pressure

Blood Pressure Of The Patients											
	123/103	123/74	125/80	126/84	130/80	130/85	130/88	131/91	132/81	133/91	Total
Mild Anxiety	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Moderate Anxiety	1	0	4	1	5	2	1	0	0	0	14
Sever Anxiety	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	4
Total	1	1	5	1	6	2	1	1	1	1	20

Table No.4.8 Next 15 patient’s association between preoperative anxiety and blood pressure

Blood Pressure Of The Patients											
	134/78	135/80	138/83	138/85	138/92	140/75	140/90	145/90	145/92	149/90	Total
Mild Anxiety	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moderate Anxiety	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sever Anxiety	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	15
Total	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	15
	Blood Pressure Of The Patients										
	160/100	160/70	160/80	160/90	167/104	168/106	170/88	Total			
Mild Anxiety	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Moderate Anxiety	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Sever Anxiety	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	9			
Total	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	9			
	P-vlaue					0.039					

Figure No.4.9 Association between preoperative anxiety and patient's blood pressure

According to Table 4.6, 4.7, 4.8 and 4.9 the obtained p-value is 0.039, indicating that the results are significant. The results shows there is a significant association between preoperative anxiety and blood pressure of the patients undergoing endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS).

Examining the association between preoperative anxiety and recovery of the patient from endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS):

Endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS) recovery times may differ depending on the patient's level of anxiety; in this study, there were 13 patients with mild anxiety, 32 with moderate anxiety, and 28 with severe anxiety. Patients with low anxiety typically transition and recover more quickly during the recovery phase; their anxiety levels may decrease significantly more quickly, enabling them to return to normal more quickly. However, recovering may take longer and require more help for patients who have substantial anxiety.

DISCUSSIONS

The aim of this study was to investigate the association between preoperative anxiety and several physiological indicators (Blood pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation and pain level) in patient undergoing endoscopic

ultrasonography (EUS). The findings of our study are consistent with the findings of the prior investigation, which likewise examined the impact of preoperative anxiety on postoperative outcomes in various surgical groups.

The study conducted by Bayrak *et al.*, increased heart rate, blood pressure, and SpO₂ levels were observed to significantly associated with greater anxiety ratings in patients having elective cholecystectomy (10). This is consistent with our findings, which showed that heart rate and blood pressure were significantly associated with preoperative anxiety during EUS. Anxiety has an impact on these physiological responses as seen by raised heart rates and blood pressure seen in patients with severe anxiety.

The study conducted by Ali *et al.*, preoperative anxiety was assessed in relation to surgery patients' recovery results (41). The results of our study concur with theirs, since we find out a strong association between preoperative anxiety and blood pressure during EUS, indicating that

anxiety may affect postoperative recovery and outcomes.

Similarly, the study by Zeev *et al.*, anxious youngsters had a more painful recovery process after tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy, requiring greater doses of painkillers, and they also had postoperative anxiety and sleep issues. The amount of anxiety experienced during EUS was significantly associated with preoperative anxiety in our study, as well. Anxiety may lead to greater pain perception during surgery as evidenced by the fact that patients with extreme anxiety had higher pain scores. For fearful young children, adenoid and tonsillectomy procedures result in increased anxiety and difficulties sleeping. Using our study, we find out a strong association between preoperative anxiety and post-EUS pain levels. Patients who experience extreme anxiety throughout the operation demonstrate how anxiety may make the surgery seem more painful (38).

According to our findings and other research, preoperative anxiety can significantly affect physiological responses and postoperative outcomes in various surgical groups. Patients undergoing EUS must deal with their preoperative anxiety in order to improve their overall experience and recovery. Implementing treatments like relaxation techniques, counselling, or anxiety management techniques may assist to enhance patient comfort and outcomes during EUS surgeries, as Achmet Ali's study pointed shown. Overall, this study adds to the expanding body of research that demonstrates the necessity of treating preoperative anxiety in surgical patients, particularly those receiving EUS. Healthcare providers may improve endoscopic ultrasonography patients' overall quality of care by comprehending and controlling anxiety. This will increase patient well-being, optimise recovery, and overall patient care.

CONCLUSIONS

There is significant association between preoperative anxiety and pain, heart rate, and blood pressure during EUS were found. Patients with extreme anxiety had higher degrees of pain,

faster heartbeats, and higher blood pressure, suggesting that worry may have a significant influence on these physiological reactions. Preoperative anxiety and respiratory rate or oxygen saturation, however, did not appear to be significantly associated. This implies that anxiety might not have a major impact on these particular physiological markers during the EUS technique.

Limitations:

- The generalizability of the results may be limited by the study's small sample size of 60 patients, which may not accurately reflect the complexity and variety of the population receiving endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS).
- The study did not fully explore or account for any potential factors that could have an impact on the findings, such comorbidities or medication use.
- The study did not take into account any additional variables that would have an impact on the degree of the patients' pain and anxiety, such as their medical histories, prior trauma, or socioeconomic circumstances.
- Because the study only involved patients getting endoscopic ultrasonography, its applicability to other medical procedures or disorders is restricted.

Recommendations:

- Examine the long-term effects of preoperative anxiety on patients' healing and quality of life after endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS) in longitudinal studies.
- Examine the effectiveness of specific intervention strategies, such as preoperative education, mindfulness-based techniques, or music therapy, in reducing preoperative anxiety and improving patient outcomes during EUS.
- Examine the effects of healthcare personnel communication and bedside manner on patients' feelings of anxiety and their overall experience throughout the EUS procedure.
- It is important to take into account

how cultural and socioeconomic factors impact preoperative anxiety in patients undergoing EUS in order to successfully manage anxiety in a range of patient groups.

- Create support groups for patients getting EUS so they have a place to share experiences and coping techniques, reducing preoperative anxiety and fostering emotional fortitude.

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